

PECULIARITIES APPLICATIONS TAX BENEFITS AND PREFERENCES IN ENTREPRENEURIAL ACTIVITIES

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Abstract: The article deals with theoretical questions ratio in the taxation system of terms such as tax relief and preference. The concept and essence of tax privileges and preferences, types and criteria for tax exemptions. based on the analysis conclusions that their similarities and distinctive features. And withdrawn proposals and theoretical recommendations of the scientific approach to the separation of these concepts.

Keywords: taxation, tax system, term, tax benefit, tax preference, rate, base, deductions, tax credit, deferral, privilege.

Introduction

During the years of independence, a favorable investment climate, a wide system of legal guarantees and benefits for stimulating the activities of business entities. In Uzbekistan held systemic Job on improvement tax legislation, phased decrease tax load, improvement and simplification systems taxation from simultaneous adoption measures on raising security taxpayers from unreasonable interference in their economic activity.

"In conditions transition to market relations taxes become main regulator in the implementation of economic policy. Essential Function tax system - its stimulating effect on the development of production" [one]. "It is necessary to ensure that the tax system bears not only and not so much fiscal, but, before Total, stimulating character, prompted any taxpayer, natural or legal person not to evade taxes, not to divert incomes into the "shadow", but, on the contrary, to strive for the development of production, increase their income" [2].

In conditions formation and development market relations important function taxes is an stimulating role in economy, So how from help taxes state carries out regulation economic conditions production and implementation goods, services, and this creates a certain "tax climate" for the economic activities of entities entrepreneurship.

The incentive function of taxes is one of the important functions of the tax system that has an active impact on the development of production, effective use of material and raw materials, financial and labor resources accumulated property, then eat across decline tax burden can stimulate the development of production,

strengthen the financial condition and revitalize investment activity. Tax regulation implemented across system tax benefits and preferences.

Often not only in scientific publications, but also in practical work as synonym concepts "tax privileges" used concept "tax preferences." but necessary delimit data economic terms, as they carry different implications for taxpayers at them application[11].

Despite the frequent mention in theory and practice of the concepts of "tax privileges" and "tax preferences", to date time not happened single definition data terms.

Article 24 of the Tax Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan lists the mandatory elements of any tax: object of taxation, taxable base, rate, calculation procedure, tax period, order representation tax reporting and order payment. IN this same article in item 3 said what "In cases, envisaged hereby code, at establishing tax and another mandatory payment in tax legislation may envisaged privileges on him, but also grounds for them applications taxpayer." So Thus, the tax benefit can be attributed to facultative, non-mandatory elements tax.

IN compliance co Art. thirty TK Uzbekistan "Benefits on taxes and others compulsory payments recognized provided separate categories taxpayers envisaged hereby code, other laws And decisions President Republic Uzbekistan Benefits on comparison from others taxpayers including possibility not pay tax And(or) another mandatory payment or pay them in a smaller amount" [5]. Such same picture can see And in Russian legislation.

Mandatory elements taxes are listed in art.17 TK and definition "tax privileges on taxes and fees" indicated in Art. 56 TK [6].

TO unfortunately in economic literature not So often meets definition such concepts, how "tax preference". That's why more often Total between tax privilege and tax preferences put sign equality.

Theoretical analysis term tax privileges.

To distinguish and define the terms "benefits" and "preferences" by us studied numerous sources, among which research and works domestic and foreign scientists and specialists dealing with in this area. And on the basis of a critical analysis, we will reveal their relationship friend from friend.

IN educational allowances under editorial A.V. Bryzgalina [22] indicated what

“A tax benefit is an exclusive legal possibility complete or partial release from payment tax at availability object taxation, but also other softening tax burden for the taxpayer.

S.G. Pepelev [23] did not define the tax benefits, but singled out three large groups of tax benefits: exemption, rebates and tax credits, uniting them in one general goal - reduction size tax obligations taxpayer.

A.V. Perov [25] thinks what tax privileges - "this any exceptions from general regulations taxation, provided in established law okay for individual categories taxpayers."

E.N. Evstigneev [15] believes that tax incentives are used to cuts size tax obligations taxpayer and for postponement or installment payment.

L.P. Pavlova [24] believes what tax benefit - this complete or partial release taxpayer from payment tax in compliance from current legislation.

N.G. Dmitrieva, D.B. Dmitriev . [14] believe that tax incentives are partial or complete release taxpayers from payment taxes.

In the textbook edited by N.V. Milyakova [21] states that the tax a benefit is a partial or complete release of physical and legal persons from paying taxes.

I.A. Maiburov [19] believes that the tax benefit is an optional element providing characterizing tax legislation individual categories taxpayers exceptional benefits including possibility not pay taxes or pay smaller size, but also other softening tax burden for taxpayer.

B.H. Alieva [nine] thinks what tax benefit - this granted tax legislation exceptional possibility softening tax burden for taxpayer (withdrawals, discounts, taxloans).

THEM. Alexandrov [8] thinks what tax benefit - this decline size taxation or providing subject tax advantages on relation to another payer.

O.V. Kachur [17] thinks what tax benefit - this complete or partial release subject from tax in compliance current legislation .

O.V. Skvortsov [26] supposes what tax benefit - this complete or partial release subject from tax in compliance current legislation (taxable minimum, tax vyety , decrease rates).

A.V. Aronov , V.A. Kashin [10] think what tax benefit - this provision of discounts , deductions, etc. by law . from the tax base and amounts accrued taxes. (liberation, discounts, loans delays,shelters).

IN brief dictionary economic terms V.G.Slagoda [eighteen] given following definition: "tax privileges - complete or partial release certain categories physical And legal persons from payment taxes."

From domestic authors , I.A. Zavalishina [16] believes that the tax benefit - this providing preveligey legislation separate categories taxpayers complete or partial release from payment taxes.

professors A.V. Vahobov And A.S. Zhuraev [12] think, what tax benefit - this providing legislation separate categories taxpayers of exceptional benefits, including the possibility of not pay taxes partially, temporarily or fully, but also in others forms. Kinds, mechanism actions and criteria tax benefits established proceeding from from development economic and social level states.

A.A. Yuldashev [31] believes that a tax benefit is the provision advantage

over another payer. Taxes are not charged in big sizes and soften tax burden taxpayers. Taxpayers do not have the opportunity to apply all tax benefits, because it takes a lot of bureaucracy and commitment. tax incentives for direct affect on the tax base and to decrease admission.

Professor K.A.Yakhyaev [32] believes , what tax benefit - this possibility complete or partial release from payment tax, softening tax burden or pay smaller size for taxpayer. He also believes that the term "tax preference" more wide concept And reveals essence much how "tax benefit."

Professors Sh. Gataulin [13] and T.S. Malikov [20] believe that the tax benefit - this complete or partial reduction size tax obligations taxpayer postponement or installments payment (discounts, protrusions, rate reduction etc.).

Theoretical analysis term tax preferences:

Preferences (from *lat. praeferentis - preference*) are advantages, privileges, provided separate states, enterprises, organizations for support certain species activities; carried out in the shape of decrease taxes, discounts customs duties, release from payments, providing beneficial loans, from purpose stimulation species activities, recognized state priority in cases compliance them conditions, envisaged legislation [27].

Preference — preference, benefit, provided to whom or, special terms use how or taxes And customs duties co discounts and benefits[28].

A.S. Balandina [eleven] gives the following definition tax preferences, which indicates the main difference between preferences and benefits - mandatory character: "tax preference - providing state benefits to certain categories of taxpayers in the form of reducing the amount of tax liabilities, which are mandatory, by conditions of counter obligations from the side taxpayer."

N.V. Milyakov [21] thinks what preferences - this special(preferred) benefits granted by one state to another on beginnings reciprocity or in unilateral okay without dissemination on the third countries; most often applied in the form of discounts or cancellation of customs duties. preferences inside countries introduced in form investment tax credit (tax deferral) and targeted tax credit for funding investment And innovative costs.

A.A. Yuldashev [31] believes what tax preference - this providing benefits legislation separate categories taxpayers full or partial exemption from taxes. Taxpayers do not have the opportunity to apply all tax benefits, because that it takes a lot bureaucracy and obligations.

N.N. Tyutyuryukov , G.B. Ternopolskaya , V.N. Tyutyuryukov [29], which believe what tax preference - this providing state benefits separate categories taxpayers in form decrease amounts of tax liabilities in various ways: by reducing tax rates, excluding objects of taxation, changing the terms of payment taxes (fees), the introduction of reducing coefficients in the calculation of taxes (fees), which

the taxpayer is obligated to execute.

Methodology research

methodological basis research amounted to analysis and synthesis, generalization, systemic an approach, methods comparative analysis. In article studied legal acts legislation, research and works domestic and foreign scientists and specialists for differences and definitions of the terms "benefits" and "preferences" dealing with issues in given areas.

The Tax Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan does not provide definitions "preferences" necessary demarcate and rosary define data concepts.

According to our opinion, tax credit can be considered how rightthe taxpayer to reduce the tax base, but the obligation. preference same, in my turn, should consider, how dutytaxpayer which gives to him possibility decrease tax base.

Thus, with all the variety of definitions of tax benefits opinions all authors converge in one - what tax privileges always mean that, along with the general procedure for taxation exists fnd special order, directed on the then, what tax the payer's obligation to be performed, i.e. paid, is reduced or decreases. However, in our opinion, such an understanding of the tax benefit narrows economic characteristic given concepts, so how main The purpose of the tax credit is not only to reduce tax burden but And achievement at this certain tasks.

That is, in a narrow understanding of the essence of a tax benefit, such norms of laws that lead to a decrease in the tax exemption itself. At more wide approach tax privileges present yourself any advantage individual categories taxpayers in front of others.

In difference from tax preferences under tax benefits implied Benefits in opportunities non-payment all or parts amounts of tax granted for a short period of time and having relatively unstable character.

Basic purpose introductions tax benefits and preferences, is an decline tax loads for taxpayers in purposes stimulation implementation them activities. but mechanism providing tax benefits and preferences different.

Tax incentives are subject to more control and administration co sides tax bodies, So how they separately are declared in tax reporting of taxpayers, which allows you to track withdrawals specific amounts. Moreover, tax incentives stand out in the statistical tax reporting on special forms. preferences same not have documentary reflections in similar reports.

Consider these concepts on the example of three taxes: a single tax payment, a flat tax for entrepreneurs and a tax on property individuals (table one).

So the way comparing concepts "tax privilege" And "tax preference", can formulate the following copyright definitions tax breaks and preferences:

tax benefit - this providing legislation individual

categories taxpayers possibility not pay taxes orpay a smaller amount, reduce the

amount of tax liabilities, as well as other softening tax burden for taxpayer.

tax preference (from *lat. praeferentis - preference*) - this providing state benefits in sphere taxation, enterprises, organizations and entrepreneurs in purposes formation favorable investment climate and business environment, but So same for support certain species activities.

It can be noted that the types of tax benefits are not specifically defined. as well as scientists and professionals. Also in scientific works, types of tax benefits have varied character. Foreign the authors define the following kinds tax benefits: complete or partial release, decrease taxable base, decline tax rates, not taxable minimum, deductions, discounts, postponement, tax amnesty and etc.

According to rating authoritative World economic forum Uzbekistan is among the five countries with the fastest growing economies in world on results of 2014-2015 And growth forecasts for 2016-2017.

It should be noted that on October 27, the World Bank Group published report "Keeping business 2016: grade quality And efficiency regulation" (Doing business 2016: Measuring Regulatory Quality and efficiency). Uzbekistan in the new ranking has risen by 16 positions compared to from last year - from 103rd to **87th place** among 189 countries [33]. also in report World jar "Keeping business 2017: Equal opportunities for all" (Doing Business 2017: Equal Opportunities for All) Uzbekistan retained mine rating and occupied **87th a place among 190 countries** [4].

Government country paid huge Attention on creation conditions for the development and improvement of the tax system. Favorable investment climate and business Wednesday, but also created tax infrastructure, allowed raise national tax system on the new world-class.

Conclusions and suggestions

Study of theoretical aspects terms « tax privilege" And "tax preference", as well as the study of their essence, content and conducted analysis, allows US withdraw the following conclusions:

do present time in legislation missing definition concepts "tax preference", not defined clear criteria demarcations concepts of "tax privilege" And "tax preference".

basic purpose introductions tax benefits and preferences is and decline tax loads for taxpayers in purposes stimulation implementation them activities. but mechanism providing tax benefits and preferences different.

kinds tax benefits in scientific works have varied character, but also co sides scientists and specialists specifically not decided.

at establishing new tax benefits or other preferences, appropriate clearly define goals, which required reach from application specified tax arrangements.

consequences providing tax benefits may have how negative, So and positive

effect.

there is no approved methodology for assessing the effectiveness of tax incentives and there is no legally established mechanism for monitoring tax benefits.

In purposes raise efficiency tax benefits and improvements business environment for business entities the following recommendations and suggestions for further improvement of the tax systems:

definition clear criterion demarcations concepts "tax privilege" And "tax preference", but also definition major species tax incentives in scientific literature;

introduction clear definitions term "tax preference" in article thirty Tax Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

repeal of the norm of the Tax Code on tax incentives, which are duplicated not relevant and ineffective.

formation unified methods estimates efficiency tax benefits And holding mechanism monitoring tax incentives;

providing tax vacation on the two of the year from moment them registration and application zero rate single tax payment for newly created small businesses in the areas of food production products, but also scientific and innovative activity;

in order to reduce the tax burden for a public enterprise nutrition reduce bet unified tax payment from 10 percent before 8percent.

➤ application order classification subjects small business on such criterion how through definitions size gross revenue;

➤ provision of benefits to reduce the taxable base of the unified social payment for the amount of accrued wages for two years subjects small business, creating workers places behind check graduates.

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